

EFFICIENT FAILURE PREDICTION METHODOLOGY FOR HIGH ASPECT RATIO COMPOSITE WINGS WITH HIGH BEND-TWIST COUPLING

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ABSTRACT

As efficiency gains in traditional aircraft designs become more incremental, high aspect ratio wings offer vastly improved aerodynamic performance but introduce complex aeroelastic and structural challenges. Innovative structural concepts for this type of wings lack corresponding sizing methods for early-stage design. This work presents a novel methodology to predict composite failure in such wings, using as a proof of concept a wing featuring a novel Z-beam wingbox structure. Our approach combines a machine learning-based surrogate model for failure prediction with a non-linear aeroelastic solver. We use superelements to represent structural configurations within a global aircraft model, enabling efficient aeroelastic response analysis. Global aircraft-level strain data is then used to compute composite ply-level failure indices of critical components using an evolved LaRC05 criterion. This enables early-stage design evaluation of innovative composite wing structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to get closer to the established net-zero goals, the aeronautics industry is making changes on their aircraft for these to be more efficient. Composite materials, especially Carbon Fibre Reinforced Polymers (CFRP), have played a major role in enabling the development of lighter and more efficient aircraft, such as the Airbus A350. Other important contributors (at the aircraft level) for the increase of efficiency are better engines, and wing geometry. As the gains in efficiency in aircraft have been asymptotically stagnating with the current, well established, design philosophies, other solutions are being investigated by the industry and the scientific community. One of the most promising solutions are very high aspect ratio wings, which are known to provide higher aerodynamic efficiency. However, the increased span introduces important changes that need to be carefully addressed at the structural sizing stage. Composite failure due to non-linearities, increased aeroelastic effects and increased-bending moments, is one of the main problems that arises when considering larger spans.

Bend-twist coupling (BTC) is a feature that allows to reduce the undesirable effects of high aspect ratio wings. This effect can be either induced by using specific material properties and/or orientations, such as tow-steered composites or by wing structures which inherently present this type of behaviour. One example of the latter is Airbus's patented Z-beam wingbox [1] (Fig. 1), which can provide different levels of coupling for aeroelastic tailoring.

Figure 1: Z-beam concept in a high aspect ratio wing [2].

However, these novel architectures exhibit a complex composite failure response, especially due to their geometric complexity. This requires high-fidelity ply-level finite element modelling to achieve accurate structural sizing, leading to an unsurmountable computational expense at the sizing stage. This challenge is further exacerbated by the necessity of accounting for non-linear geometric effects in simulations, so that the estimated loads are not overly conservative. Consequently, there is a pressing need for efficient predictive frameworks capable of evaluating ply-level composite failure during the early design stages, where numerous structural configurations must be assessed efficiently.

In this work, we highlight a novel methodology to efficiently predict failure of composite components in high aspect ratio wings. It uses a machine learning based surrogate model [2] with an evolved [3,4] version of LaRC05 [5] for ply-level failure prediction (Fig. 2), which is coupled to a non-linear aeroelastic solver. We then developed a bespoke superelement to insert the novel wingbox concept in the outer part of the wing in a full aircraft model. Knowing the aeroelastic response, we are then able to obtain the failure indices of critical parts of the wingbox from macroscale loads.

(a) Matrix cracking

(b) Fibre kinking

Figure 2: Examples of failure mechanisms that can be predicted by the failure model [5].

In conclusion, this study presents an innovative framework that solves the problem of efficient prediction of failure indices in critical regions of high-aspect-ratio composite wings during sizing. Its adaptability makes it particularly valuable for early-stage analysis of any unconventional structures, offering flexibility for researchers and industry engineers to implement custom modifications.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology has two separate main parts, at two very different scales. One is a surrogate model to predict ply-level damage and the other is a non-linear aeroelastic solver to simulate the full aircraft behaviour. The physics guided machine learning based surrogate model, takes as input the homogenised strains in the wingbox and its design variables, and returns the failure index of a critical detail, in this case, bolted joints [2]. Additionally, the homogenised stiffness matrix of the wingbox is obtained, which will allow its inclusion in the aircraft model. An overview schematic of the surrogate model is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Multiscale analysis sequence for the prediction of ply-level failure indices [2].

The failure indices used for the surrogate model come from a detailed finite element model of the bolted connection, and are calculated using an evolved [3,4] LaRC05 [5] failure criterion. To simulate the aircraft response, a non-linear aeroelastic solver, FENIAX [6], is used. It uses the vibration modes of the condensed aircraft model to calculate the non-linear response (Fig.4).

Figure 4: Workflow to obtain aeroelastic solution using FENIAX. After [6].

Superelements are then used to provide the required stiffness properties to the Global Finite Element Model (GFEM) of the aircraft. This approach is specifically useful since it allows to directly change only the outer part of the wing, not having to generate a full aircraft model for each design iteration. Additionally, since only the internal structure of the wing is being changed, i.e. there is no change in chord or airfoil shape, the aerodynamic characteristics are preserved for the entire procedure. A schematic of the overall methodology is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: Overview of the methodology for composite failure prediction. After [2,6].

3 RESULTS

As a proof of concept of the multiscale structural analysis described in this work, a static follower vertical load of 21500 N is applied to both wingtips of the Bristol Ultra Green (BUG) model [7]. In this paper, a sequence of 10 Z-Beam wingboxes (as presented in Ref. [2]) is used to cover the last 11.28 m of each wing (section 3 of the wing in Ref. [7]). The homogenised strains of the first Z-beam wingbox, counted from the fuselage toward the wingtip, under the applied load (14 time steps), are presented in the failure index map shown in Fig. 6. As bending strain increases, a corresponding increase in torsional strain magnitude is observed, attributed to the bend-twist coupling characteristics inherent in the wingbox design.

Figure 6: Prediction of matrix cracking failure mode in the outer part of a high aspect ratio aircraft [5].

The analysis reveals that matrix cracking failure occurs at the bolted joint under this loading condition. This failure mode demonstrates the effective integration of disparate length scales within the structural model, as illustrated in the figure. The coupling between local joint-level failure mechanisms and global structural response highlights the multi-scale nature of this work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we present a multidisciplinary methodology for the efficient prediction of ply level failure in high aspect ratio composite wings. By leveraging a previously developed machine learning-based surrogate model, we accurately capture the failure behaviour of a novel composite component designed to induce bend–twist coupling. Applied to the outer wing region of a full-scale aircraft, this approach enables effective structural sizing by bridging vastly different scales, spanning at least five orders of magnitude. This methodology offers a modular and computationally efficient solution, making it adaptable to existing industrial and research workflows and thereby supporting early-stage design exploration and optimisation.

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